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White Paper on User Centred Design to Address Challenges in the Design and Creation of Agricultural Data Visualisation Interfaces

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Abstract: The increase in agricultural data has created a need for developing tools that can manage, share, and visualise this information, while also being accessible to farmers. The use of different technical languages, varying needs, and differing objectives for the tools being developed and used creates a gap between technology developers and farmers, leading to inefficient information transfer. Consequently, interfaces are often poorly adapted to the real needs of end-users and lack essential functionality. This white paper aims to propose a User-Centred Design methodology in order to address the challenges encountered in creating interfaces for shared agricultural Data Space Ecosystems. The proposed methodology, an adaptation of ISO 9241:210-2019, highlights the importance of user participation at various stages of the interface design cycle for the creation of user-adaptive technologies.

Keywords: interface design; user centre design; data space ecosystem; agricultural data

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1. Introduction

Historically, farming has played a fundamental role in our society and has gradually moved on to what we know today as Precision Agriculture (PA) [1]. PA uses advanced technologies like sensors and IoT to monitor farms and improve resource efficiency, productivity, and sustainability [2]. This approach generates vast amounts of data from sources such as ground sensors [3], field sampling [4], and remote sensing [5,6]. However, managing these data are challenging due to its fragmentation and diverse storage formats, complicating comprehensive analysis and integration [7]. Furthermore, issues such as data standardization, interoperability, privacy, and security further complicate the digitalisation of agriculture [8,9]. Addressing these concerns is vital for effective data management and decision-making in modern agriculture.

In addition to optimizing resource efficiency and sustainability, PA also aims to enhance operational efficiency while minimizing socio-economic and environmental impacts [10]. The integration of IoT plays a crucial role in generating diverse and vast amounts of data that must be efficiently stored, managed, and analysed [11]. Nonetheless, the complexity of handling these datasets increases due to the involvement of multiple stakeholders, which exacerbates issues such as data fragmentation, standardization, and interoperability [12].

In this context, Data Space Ecosystems (DSE) address the challenges associated with the digitalisation of agricultural data [13]. By providing a unified framework for data integration and management, DSE can mitigate problems such as those mentioned above. Through common data standards and protocols, DSE promotes data standardisation and facilitates data sharing by reducing data fragmentation. In addition, DSE improves data accuracy by consolidating disparate data sources into a coherent system, allowing for more reliable analysis and insights. Privacy and security concerns are also addressed in a DSE framework, which can implement robust data protection measures and access controls. By

centralising and standardising data while promoting collaboration between stakeholders, DSE significantly improves the efficiency and effectiveness of digital agricultural solutions [14]. Ultimately, DSEs play a crucial role in transforming PA, allowing secure data access and exchange, facilitating informed decision-making, and promoting sustainable practices [15].

While DSE would facilitate access to large datasets and analytical tools, empowering farmers to optimise their actions, boost productivity and mitigate risks, a significant challenge remains: many of the current technical tools and dashboards for data management are difficult for end-users, particularly farmers, to use effectively. The distinct characteristics of agricultural data, such as formats, frequency, and application fields, create a variety of visualisation possibilities. To ensure these tools meet the needs and digital capabilities of end-users, it is essential to involve them in the dashboard design process.

In this regard, User-Centred Design (UCD) methods can propose a tailored solution, through the active involvement of users in both design and evaluation phases [16]. By focusing on UCD, technological solutions can be better aligned with the needs of primary users in the agricultural sector. Several studies highlight the importance of well-designed graphical interfaces that apply the UCD methodology to develop tools adapted to end-users' needs and capabilities [17,18]. As agricultural digitization increasingly involves the creation of data visualisations tools, ensuring that these tools align with the digital capabilities of agricultural data consumers becomes critical. This requires robust strategies during the design process to ensure data is managed and transformed into valuable insights for appropriate use [19].

User participation at different stages of the design cycle can be facilitated using techniques such as interviews, questionnaires, role-playing, and simulations, as well as usability testing [20]. As UCD methods are generally considered to improve product usefulness and usability, their consideration in the design of agricultural data visualisation tools is supposed to boost the creation of intuitive data visualisations tailored to the needs of farmers. This methodology ensures continuous interaction between technical developers and end-users throughout the development process.

The need for effectively adapted interfaces in the agriculture sector resonates in recent European research efforts to make these technologies accessible to end-users. Among these initiatives, several European H2020 projects have emerged, such as LIFT [21], DEMETER [22], and DIVINE [23], which aim to merge the efforts between farmers and domain experts in the agriculture sector to create technologies and AI-based methods that harness the power of a data economy in agriculture, designed to offer beneficial tools for the agricultural industry. Furthermore, they seek to provide solutions to a series of problems that arise in this sector. In particular, the DIVINE project aims to create a DSE where users with different profiles can store, access, and consult their private, public, and shared data.

A key challenge in this context is data fragmentation, typically resulting from the diverse data models and semantics used in the industry. This issue was addressed in the aforementioned H2020 DEMETER project through the creation of the Agricultural Information Model (AIM). AIM aligns with existing standards to enable data integration and interoperability across distinct agricultural frameworks [24]. Similarly, within the DIVINE project, the process of generating data catalogues and services also provides a solution to the problem of data fragmentation while highlighting the diversity of commercial platforms and prototypes under development. This diversity presented both a challenge and an opportunities for improving the integration and unification of various visualisation tools, ultimately enhancing users' access to and interpretation of agricultural data.

However, while these visualisation tools hold great potential in terms of robustness and scalability, many existing dashboards for data management and visualisation present opportunities for improvement in effectively conveying the distinct characteristics of the information or data they represent, providing a chance to enhance clarity and user experience. The fundamental challenge of a dashboard design is to display data clearly without distractions and in a way that can be examined and understood quickly. Although

ecosystems of shared spaces offer great potential for farm analysis and management, they often fail to be functional for end-users, as farmers struggle with interpreting and handling the complex data [25].

For a proper design of the dashboards and visualisations in the DSE, it is essential to let the target audience and the data guide the design. To ensure the creation of long-life products and avoid developing interfaces that are difficult to understand, it is important to define and the main characteristics of the end-user of the application's end-user and their goals.

This white paper proposes a UCD methodology adapted from ISO 9241:210-2019 [26] in order to address the difficulties encountered during the process of creating interfaces that will be the basis for the creation of agricultural data visualisation within a shared data ecosystem. More specifically, this study analyses the implementation trial of UCD methodology to fill the gaps in today's agricultural data visualisation interfaces, detailing the developed surveys and indicating the identified minimal requirements.

This white paper is divided into several sections. Section 2 explains the process to overcome the problems detected in the creation of interfaces for the management and visualisation of agricultural data. Each of the described steps follows the criteria of the ISO standard. This procedure includes: (1) meetings with pilot representatives, (2) identifying useful features and visualisation needs, (3) creating mockups, and (4) a survey for feedback. Each step follows ISO standard criteria. Section 3 presents the findings for each step. Section 4 reviews these findings and the challenges faced. The paper ends with Section 5, summarising key points and suggesting future directions.

2. Methodology Proposition

The methodology proposed in this paper is based on the international standard ISO 9241:210 which provides the guidelines for UCD for interactive systems. This document describes the requirements and the steps for a user experience-centred interactive system design summarised in Table 1 and Figure 1. It emphasizes involving users throughout the process of system development, in order to prioritize their preferences and needs in the design. Although the methodology defined in this standard includes several steps to create a prototype and evaluate it according to user requirements, this work only presents the implementation trial developed until Step 3, which covers the procedure up to mockup creation and the identification of user-system useful functionalities. Table 1 and Figure 1 defines the goal of each of those steps, the expected outcome, and the activities developed during this study in order to address the challenges encountered in creating an interface for the visualisation and management of agricultural data.

Table 1. Main steps based on ISO 9241:210 standards definition. Highlighted in yellow are those covered in the present work.

Step	Goal	Output	Activity
1	Understand and specify the context of use	Context of use description	Meetings with the pilots representatives
2	Specify the user requirements	User needs description User requirements specification	Common functionality extraction Mockup creation
3	Produce design solutions to meet the requirements	User-system interaction specification User interface specification Implemented user interface	Survey based on the created mockups Evaluation metrics
4	Evaluate the designs against requirements	Evaluation results Conformance test results Long-term monitoring result	

Figure 1. Flowchart describing the phases of the proposed methodology.

It has to be mentioned that this paper aims to propose a procedure in response to the communication challenges that emerged during the design and creation of a prototype intended to give access and visualisation of distinct agriculture data services within the DIVINE project [23]. This project is developing an Agricultural DSE [27], in order to facilitate secure interconnection of existing agri-data spaces. The functionalities that enable this exchange are discovery, registration, management of federated agri-data spaces, and visualisation of available data catalogues among others. The creation of the visualisation service for distinct data and services highlighted challenges that emerged during the convergence of user interface specifications motivated the present analysis in a white paper format on the importance of end-user collaboration and their representation in determining the useful functionalities of the system or prototype that is under development.

The process of following the Steps 1–3 proposed by the methodology in Table 1 and Figure 1 has been motivated by many obstacles commonly encountered in the digitisation of agriculture. Table 2 summarises the most challenging difficulties in creating agricultural technology systems that involves end-users with distinct data sources, data exploitation goals, and technology use capabilities.

This white paper summarises the barriers encountered during the process of creating a data exploration and exploitation interface for diverse agricultural profiles, as these difficulties are common or recurring in the agriculture sector, as highlighted in Table 2. Additionally, it outlines the procedure followed to address these identified barriers, which is based on a user-centred methodology. In conclusion, this white paper aims to contribute a procedure adapted from ISO 9241:210, as detailed in Table 1 and Figure 1 in order to address the emerged challenges.

This work is part of the aforementioned European DIVINE program [23]. The main goal of this project is to create an ecosystem for sharing agricultural data between the public and private sectors, improving data interoperability, transparency, and trust. It will assess the benefits of data sharing, establish governance models, and involve stakeholders in co-creating solutions. In order to securely manage the farmers' personal or sensitive data, the data privacy and security of the agri-food application platform is handled by the CredSSI [28], a tool that implements a Self-Sovereign Identity model for Identity Management. The project also focuses on developing new business models and demonstrating their impact through pilot testing. Several meetings were held with representatives from four different pilot projects, which are key participants in the DIVINE program. These pilots contribute by providing real-world data and scenarios, helping to shape and validate the ecosystem. A brief description of the pilots is provided below, with further details available in Table A1 of Appendix A.

Table 2. Challenges in the development of agricultural technology systems

Challenges	Description	Refs.
Language	Technicians developing the technology and end-users (farmers) have different technical languages. This communication gap complicates understanding and collaboration. Developers often lack experience in agricultural technology, making it difficult to design appropriate functionalities and represent data optimally. Conversely, farmers struggle to communicate their needs due to limited knowledge in technology development.	[29,30]
Needs	Farmers and livestock farmers have diverse needs, making it difficult to create visualizations of common data spaces. Additionally, users' familiarity with technology varies: frequent users prioritize usability, while infrequent users emphasize ease of learning.	[31]
Objectives/Goals	Developers and end-users often have different objectives in building the technology, leading to a lack of common understanding. The task and its goals should serve as a proper reference for the design.	[32]
Existence of Other Tools	Many users already use other platforms for data sharing and visualization, leading to low interest in new tools. Farmers often use smartphones for decision-making, with 95% using smartphones and 71% using specific apps for crop information and pest or disease detection.	[33]
Building trust in data sharing	The trust between data providers and consumers is the cornerstone of an efficient data sharing system. The data sharing platform will not be used if the participants who provide and consume the data do not confide in the system or one another.	[34]
Technology Familiarisation	Farmers' familiarity with technology varies widely. Traditionally, they have kept manual records for personal use. The agricultural transformation has resulted in data overload, making it hard for many farmers to manage data in the traditional way.	[35]

- R1: Slovenian non-profit Business Support Organization. Proves a discussion about Pilot Data Space for sustainable food production platforms. This pilot aims to foster cross-sectoral innovation and implementation of novel technologies and Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in rural-based sectors.
- R2: Irish research-intensive global university that helps in the discussion of the Pilot Crop yield prediction model platforms.
- R3: Greek technology company specializing in ICT that focuses on developing and implementing innovative solutions for the agriculture and data sectors, was focused on the Pilot Smart Farming data management in the service of the new Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) monitoring platforms.
- R4: Spanish farmer who discusses the potential effects of agricultural data sharing on traditional olive and almond plantations.

2.1. Understand and Specify the Context of Use

In order to understand and specify the context of the use of the interfaces to be developed, individual and group meetings were conducted with pilot representatives. From these meetings, information was primarily extracted regarding the context of use, the data to be managed, and the needs and main characteristics of the IoT and data management platforms used by the end-users. These insights, referring to the pilots (R1, R2, R3, and R4 as defined in Table A1), were collected indirectly through their representatives.

The central goal of these meetings was to evaluate the platforms and the different features and tools that pilots use for the management and the visualisation of the different data. The principal aim was to identify, in terms of data visualisation, the strengths for these users and the most valuable functionalities among those platforms. During the discussions,

pilot representatives shared their perspectives on the most favourable characteristics of the platforms they used. They also indicated their preferences and suggestions regarding the utilities and types of visualisations. In summary, the main objective is to examine real situations where users interact with existing products and to facilitate early integration through open communication and information transfer. Early integration in collaboration with end-users is a cornerstone for prioritizing the functionality of the final prototype, as highlighted in [36].

2.2. Specify the User Requirements

The objective of this section is to establish a bilateral communication between technical interface developers and end-users. The lack of a common vocabulary among these profiles, coupled with the end-users' limited technical knowledge about the available tools, has resulted in ineffective communication during the identification of useful functionalities in the data visualisation platforms within this project. In order to address this communication gap, we have proceeded with two phases as indicated in the next paragraphs. First, a list of common functionalities detected in the pilot data management platforms was created, and straightaway, several mock-ups have been illustrated based on these common functionalities. The main goal is to ask the end-users their opinion about those mock-ups to infer the most important functionalities in the data management interfaces through a survey or questionnaire.

In what follows, we describe the effort dedicated to identifying user needs and specifying their requirements. Based on these identified functionalities, a series of interface mockups were created.

2.2.1. Extract Common Useful Functionalities or Visualisation Requirements

With the intention of describing the users' needs, the information shared in the meetings was analysed to deduce common and individual characteristics. These features have been grouped into a generalized list of functionalities, and a table has been created to detail the prioritization of these functionalities among the pilots.

These requirements have been illustrated in distinct mockups created to collect feedback from end-users through a questionnaire. The purpose of the questionnaire is to determine the final functionalities needed to define a design solution that meets global user requirements. The questions are specifically focused on preferences related to agricultural data visualisation and will be used for future prototype development.

2.2.2. Mockup of Visualisations

The extracted common functionalities have been depicted in various configurations, resulting in multiple mockups. These mockups serve as the foundation for an intuitive way to interact with end-users, aligning with UCD principles in prototypes and intermediate stages. This iterative design process helps achieve user-adapted visualisations that are both functional and suitable for end-users. The mockups were designed and created using the free and open-source vector graphics editor Inkscape [37].

Another benefit of the development of mockups as indicated by [36] is that it allows end-users to understand the technological capabilities of the developers, the potential uses and representations of data, and the possible technologies that can be implemented.

2.3. Produce Design Solutions to Meet the Requirements

Following the UCD strategy defined in Table 1 and Figure 1, the measurable output of Step 3 is the specification of user interface, before starting the corresponding implementation. To this end, as indicated in Table 1 and Figure 1, it is necessary to specify the user–system interactions. This is the main goal of the present subsection, which establishes a survey based on the mockups, and evaluation metrics to converge towards these interaction specifications.

Survey

For the purpose of obtaining feedback on the created mockups, a survey has been conducted which is detailed in Appendix B. The population capable of providing valuable insights, based on their professional experience with agricultural data management and development platforms, is divided into distinct profiles and target groups, as detailed in Table 3. It should be noted that the target group TgA-B, consisting of farmers and advisors, represents the end-user profile.

Table 3. Target groups and their corresponding profiles. The groups that have participated in the survey have been highlighted in yellow colour.

Target Group	Profiles
TgA; TgB	Farmers and advisors
TgC; TgD	UE food producers industry
TgE	ICT and technologies—service providers, researchers, startups, and innovators
TgF	Researchers

Survey data were collected using Google Forms and subsequently stored and analysed using Python (version 2.7.5). The questionnaire includes a series of questions related to the functionalities and aesthetic characteristics of the various sections represented in the mockups. The nine questions that constitute the entire survey are presented in two different formats. One format corresponds to a multiple-choice option where respondents rate each of the questions, choosing between *Avoid*, *Indifferent*, or *Important*. The other format aims to gather respondents' opinions on a specific topic by demanding short text responses. The evaluation of these two formats has been developed in distinct manners.

On the one hand, the group of multiple-choice questions was examined statistically, mainly to determine whether there are significant differences between the groups analysed. For this purpose, the selected evaluation metrics are the Chi-square (χ^2) and *p*-Value statistics. On the other hand, for the group of free-response questions, a qualitative analysis was carried out based on the answers obtained.

3. Results

This section summarises the interactions, suggestions, and results that emerged during the process of creating an agricultural data exploration interface as part of the DSE. The structure of this section aligns with the framework presented in the Methodology proposition Section 2, which is based on the different stages outlined in Table 1.

3.1. Understand and Specify the Context of Use

Interviews conducted with various pilot representatives revealed that each pilot utilizes different tools for data visualisation and management. The main characteristics of these commercial or private platform or data exploitation tools are presented below.

R1: platform mainly focused on benchmarking. Farmers share their data in Excel format. This information is represented in different ways, benchmarking is performed, and the advisors extract information from this data. The platform consists of several services, including login, a main menu, production data, tables with farm information, benchmarking, and a service for advisory team recommendations.

R2: commercial platform that allows for the visualisation of data corresponding to the different crop fields. Users can visualise data through maps, tables, and graphs. As in the case of R1, this platform consists of several pages on which the different types of visualisations are distributed. In addition to the commercial tool for data visualisation, a decision tree is also being developed for optimal and automatic crop management.

R3: commercial and a private platform for the management of agricultural crops. The commercial platform, as in the other pilots, consists of different pages on which crop information is displayed through maps and tables, along with access to weather forecasts.

R4: two commercial platforms for the management of their crop data and data from the environmental sensors they have installed on their terrain. These platforms, like others, consist of multiple pages for different data visualisations.

It is important to note that, due to the technical experience of pilot representatives with existing agriculture data exploration platforms, their input may not fully reflect the actual needs of end-users, as their experiences may not represent farmers' technological abilities. In User-Centred Design, direct user interaction is crucial to obtain authentic and realistic feedback through direct engagement with farmers.

3.2. Specify the User Requirements

These sections aim to specify the basic user-system interactions. For this purpose, the essential user functionalities for agricultural data management platforms are identified and summarised in Table 4. Distinct configurations of those functionalities listed in Table 4 are depicted in various mockups, as described in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Mockups of the various interfaces for the agricultural DSE. (a) A data search engine for available datasets in the data space, allowing for searches by geographical location on a political map with additional filtering options for refined results; (b) a data search engine for available datasets in the data space, providing filtering by data characteristics; (c) data visualisation: location map, summary of intrinsic information for the selected field, comparative graphs of different fields for specific indices, and data tables; (d) a comparative data visualisation: graphs for comparing data acquired from the data ecosystem, data tables, and requests and notifications, with a direct access button to the agricultural DSE.

Table 4. Summary table of the main functionalities of the platforms that pilots use for the visualisation and management of their data.

Pilot	Functionalities					
	A	B	C	D	E	F
R1		✓	✓		✓	✓
R2	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
R3	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
R4	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	

A—Parcel identification; B—Data description through tables and maps; C—Aggregation services; D—Connection and visualisation of private and public weather station data; E—Concrete formula application (Growing Degree Calculation, temperature thresholds to compute accumulation of chilling hour); F—Decision support system.

3.2.1. Extract Common Useful Functionalities or Visualisation Requirements

The common functionalities identified for the services and visualisations of the agricultural data management platforms are presented in Table 4. While multiple functionalities were identified during these meetings, only five were considered the most essential.

Table 4 summarises the functionalities deemed crucial based on an analysis of distinct private and commercial platforms.

3.2.2. Mockup of Visualisations

Based on meetings discussions, four different mockups were generated to represent the various sections of the Agricultural DSE prototype intended for development in the DIVINE project [23]. The final version of the mockups, incorporating suggestions from pilot representatives, is shown in Figure 2. Below is a detailed description of each:

- Mockup represented in Figure 2a illustrates the data search engine interface for available data in the agricultural DSE. It features a map highlighting countries with accessible datasets. Users can first select a country, and then they can narrow down the search by choosing a specific location within that country. Finally, the data can be filtered by type for further refinement.
- Figure 2b shows an alternative approach to searching for data in the database. In this case, users can filter data by specific characteristics. Filters include data type, associated agricultural activity, country, and date range. Once the filtering is complete, datasets meeting the selected criteria are displayed.
- Mockup visualised in Figure 2c focuses on data visualisation. A map is displayed, where data is represented using colour coding. In this mockup, crop fields with available data are highlighted. Users can select a field to view its intrinsic data, such as size, location, and other static attributes. Additionally, users can choose specific indices to analyse relevant characteristics for farm management. Multiple locations can also be selected for comparative analysis between different areas.
- Figure 2d, similar to the mockup detailed in Figure 2c, emphasizes comparative data visualisation. However, in this case, users can view not only their own data but also data acquired through the data space. A feature to monitor data requests and notifications has also been added, along with a direct access button to the agricultural DSE.

3.3. Produce Design Solutions to Meet the Requirements

To develop a prototype that includes agricultural data visualisation functionalities best suited to the needs and capabilities of end-users, this section describes the survey conducted as part of the project.

3.3.1. Survey

In order to obtain feedback on the created mockups, a survey detailed in Appendix B was developed. It asked a series of questions related to the functionalities and aesthetics of

the different services represented in the mockups. The survey was conducted during the General Assembly of the DIVINE project [23], held from 20 to 22 April 2024, in Rome.

A total of 12 participants completed the survey. Given the diversity of professional profiles among the respondents, they were asked at the beginning of the survey to identify their professional profile and the entity they represented. The profile categories included *Researcher*, *Farmer*, *Livestock Keeper*, *Advisor*, and *Paying Agency*. However, only three profiles were represented in the final responses: one response from a *Farmer*, one from an *Advisor*, and ten from *Researchers* (as shown in Figure 3). It should be pointed out that this unbalance of samples between different profiles that have participated in the survey can significantly affect the results derived from the analysis of the survey.

Figure 3. Percentage of participation of the different profiles surveyed.

For completeness purposes, the survey results were examined in three ways: first, by considering all participants collectively (Part *a* of this subsection); second, by exploring variations in results based on the respondents’ profiles (Researcher, Farmer, or Advisor) (Part *b* of this subsection); and finally, by analysing the influence of the target groups defined in Table 3, which are highlighted in yellow (part *c* of this subsection).

It is important to note that the multiple-choice questions Q1, Q2, Q3, and Q6 were analysed statistically, while the open-ended questions were used to complement the discussion.

Descriptive Analysis without Categorisation

The responses to each question were analysed visually to understand the overall prioritisations of the sample. For this purpose, responses were not categorised by respondents’ profiles or target groups. The results obtained for each of the questions are shown below in Figures 4–7.

As can be observed in Figure 4, most respondents consider the ability to visualise both their own data and external data as an important feature. In both cases, fewer than 17% of respondents consider this feature *Indifferent*, and none of them expressed opposition to it.

Figure 4. Q1—How relevant these aspects are for you, where Q1-1: *Be able to visualise your own data* and Q1-2: *Be able to visualise others data*.

Figure 5 illustrates that key features such as the availability of a decision-making system (Q2-8), the visualisation and description of data from tables and maps (Q2-2), and the possibility of identifying parcels (Q2-1) were rated as essential tools and services by respondents. In contrast, the possibility to apply specific formulas (Q2-7) and the possibility to consult the status of pending agricultural DSE applications (Q2-9) were rated as unimportant by respondents.

Figure 5. Q2—Indicate the priority of the following visualisation tools or services, where Q2-1: Parcel identification; Q2-2: Data description through tables and maps; Q2-3: Benchmarking service; Q2-4: Data downloading; Q2-5: Data uploading; Q2-6: Connection and visualisation to private and public weather data; Q2-7: Concrete formula application; Q2-8: Decision support system; and Q2-9: See the status of Agricultural DSE requests.

The bar graph depicted in Figure 6 illustrates the importance of different mockup table features (e.g., colours, highlighting relevant information, and the ability to display multiple plots) based on user feedback. Across all three features, approximately 72% of respondents rated them as *Important*, while 28% considered them *Indifferent*. Notably, no respondents suggested avoiding any of these features.

Figure 6. Q3—Features of the table, where Q3-1: Colours; Q3-2: Highlight relevant information; and Q3-3: Be able to display more than one plot on each table.

Similarly, Figure 7 highlights user feedback on various chart features, showing that around 77.8% of respondents viewed various chart features (colours, highlighting relevant information, and the ability to display more than one plot) as *Important*, while 22.2% rated them as *Indifferent*. Again, no respondents indicated that any feature should be avoided.

Figure 7. Q6—Features of the chart, where Q6-1: Colours; Q6-2: Highlight relevant information; and Q6-3: Be able to display more than one plot on each table.

Evaluation Results Based on Profiles: Researchers, Farmers, and Advisors

This section focuses on analyses where statistically significant differences were found, which are summarised in Table 5 below. Analyses without significant results are included in Appendix C.1.1.

Table 5. Correlations between the different ‘profiles’ and the answers for Q1 question, where Q1-1: Be able to visualise your own data and Q1-2: Be able to visualise others data.

Sub-Question	Statistics		Result
	χ^2	p-Value	
Q1-1	11.999	0.002	Significant
Q1-2	5.520	0.063	Not Significant

As shown in Table 5, a statistically significant difference was identified between the professional profiles regarding how relevant they considered the ability to visualise their own data.

Analysis of the responses to this specific question, as shown in Figure 8, reveals that researchers and farmers rated the functionality to visualise their own data as crucial, whereas advisors regard it as less significant.

Figure 8. Percentage of the answers given for each of the profiles surveyed for the sub-question Q1-1 How relevant it is to be able to visualise your own data.

Evaluation Results Based on the Target Groups: TgA-B and TgE

The survey responses were also analysed based on the target groups defined in the Grant Agreement of the DIVINE project. In this official document several profiles are defined as specified in Table 3 in Methodology proposition Section 2. Of all the defined target groups, only Farmers and Advisors (TgA and TgB) and Researchers (TgE) participated in the survey.

Statistical tests, including χ^2 and p -Values, were applied to the target groups. However, no statistically significant differences were found. All results are reported in Appendix C.1.2.

4. Discussion

In this section, we analyse the benefits and limitations of the UCD methodology proposition, adapted from ISO 9241:210. The challenges encountered in creating interfaces for shared agricultural DSE (e.g., communication issues between developers and farmers) motivated this white paper to propose that UCD could enhance data interoperability and decision-making in smart farming through effective interface design.

In this sense, it is important to note that, due to a lack of technical vocabulary in programming and interface design on behalf of the users, they were unable to clearly identify the functionalities they considered necessary for designing or developing an interface for exploring data and service catalogues, as well as for data visualisation, both of which are essential in an agricultural data space. Moreover, the unbalance in survey sample sizes between different profiles can significantly affect the outcomes derived from the analysis. However, it is crucial to note that the principal aim of this white paper is not to draw statistically significant results, but rather to expose the difficulties encountered and propose the follow-up of the UCD methodology as a possible solution.

In this context, individual consultations with pilot representatives facilitated the extraction of functionalities and visualisation tools commonly used in digitisation platforms within the agricultural domain, ensuring better alignment with end-user needs. This approach offers a more realistic perspective on what end-users consider essential beyond just aesthetics and preferences preferences. Interface usability concerns, such as ease of interaction and data accessibility restrictions, should be analysed from the end-user's point of view to ensure the real-world applicability. Expanding the survey to assess ease of use, satisfaction with navigation, and the ability to perform specific agricultural tasks would provide a fuller picture.

Among the six most significant functionalities, the ability to represent data in both table and temporal graph formats, as well as to incorporate information derived from specific formulas or indices (functionalities labelled *B* and *E* in Table 4), is present across all platforms used for managing data. Notably, as shown in Figure 5, which illustrates the priority given by respondents to various data visualisation tools and services, 75% consider the ability to describe data using tables and maps as important (Q2-2 in Figure 5). This group includes the entire TgA-B target group, comprising farmers and advisors, who are regular end-users of DSE platforms.

Likewise, as shown in Figure 5, a majority of respondents (66.7%) consider the ability to identify the plot to which the data belongs, along with the availability of an aggregation service (functionalities *A* and *C* in Table 4) as *Important*. Both of which are present in 75% of the pilots' current crop production management and data monitoring platforms. Similar to functionalities *B* and *E*, these two were rated as *Important* by all members of the TgA-B target group.

Regarding the functionality to connect and visualise private and public weather station data (functionality *D* in Table 4), 58.4% of respondents indicated that it is an important for them (Q2-6 in Figure 5). However, the target group of end-users (TgA-B) is split between considering it *Important* and *Indifferent*.

For the decision support system (functionality *F* in Table 4), only half of the platforms currently used by farmers include this tool. However, it is worth noting, that 83.4% of respondents consider this functionality *Important* for an agricultural DSE (Q2-8 in Figure 5).

Continuing with the analysis of the questionnaire responses, Figure 4 shows that more than 83% of respondents consider the ability to visualise their own and other users' agricultural data as *Important*. Additionally, Table 5 indicates that the respondent's profile influences how important they found the ability to visualise their own data in the DSE, with each profile assigning different levels of relevance (see Figure 8).

The majority of respondents rated the use of colour in tables and charts, the option to highlight relevant information, and the ability to view multiple charts or tables simultaneously as *Important* (see Figures 6 and 7). However, no statistically significant results were found when analysing the responses to questions Q3 and Q6 in relation to profiles and target groups (see Tables A2 and A3 of Appendix C.1). In other words, belonging to a specific profile or target group does not appear to influence the importance assigned to these features.

Moreover, while respondents generally appreciated the clarity with which the data is presented in the tables, many expressed a desire for enhanced filtering capabilities. Incorporating a functionality that allows users to select and display only the desired columns or rows would enhance usability. Additionally, it was noted that the interface design appears outdated and suggested that a modern layout with neutral backgrounds and a streamlined structure would enhance the user experience.

Furthermore, respondents highlighted that the information was presented in a simple, clear, and intuitive way. Nevertheless, they point out that having the option to enlarge each of the tables to full screen and to be able to visualise the axes and headings more clearly is something that could facilitate the interpretation of data depicted on the display. Additionally, based on feedback from the free-response questions, several areas for improvement in the user experience were identified, such as the need for a responsive platform adaptable to various devices, which would significantly enhance accessibility and usability.

5. Conclusions and Future Work

This white paper aims to highlight the challenges encountered in creating interfaces for shared agricultural DSE. The main objective was to identify the essential functionalities and tools that end-users consider crucial in a shared data space in order to create a interface prototype to give access to the considered distinct services. This was accomplished by applying the ISO 9241:210-2019 methodology, to subsequently develop prototypes of functional interfaces adapted to end-users' needs. One of the main conclusions of this study is that the methodology adapted from the mentioned ISO standard provides a guidance towards the understanding between developers and end-users. This procedure enables technique designers to gain a clear understanding of specific requirements for data visualisations and interfaces from an early stage. This clarity facilitates the development of prototypes that better meet end-user expectations, thereby accelerating the creation of a successful final product.

In this study, carried out within the DIVINE project, which aims to generate interfaces for exploring data catalogues, services, and their corresponding extensions, we observed that adhering to this standard facilitates the iterative design process. In other words, it allows for greater fluidity in situations of misunderstandings between stakeholders.

However, we also concluded that the end-user group involved in the iterative design significantly influences the entire process. For the final prototype to be effective, it is essential that the final prototype must be tailored to the capabilities and needs of the end-users. In this specific case, the fact that the individual meetings have been conducted by farmers' representatives complicates the transfer of end-user preferences, opinions, and needs.

A significant challenge in this process is the inadequate sample size of respondents. This limitation affects the quality of the data, as a small sample and unbalanced distribution among different groups (profiles and target groups) may skew the results. To achieve statistically valid outcomes in future surveys, it is recommended to secure a larger, more diverse

sample with balanced representation across all participant profiles. In short, balanced samples for each group and profile relevant to the use case are necessary.

Once the meetings have taken place, it is evident that a second round of discussions, including feedback from users (particularly farmers), would be beneficial to extract further insights. Even a common meeting in which the different profiles (farmers, researchers, and advisors) could talk about different aspects related to the visualisation of agricultural data could be advantageous.

To further refine the extracted functionalities, or if necessary, adjust or combine them, we consider that organising a collective meeting where users from various profiles can discuss aspects related to the visualisation. This approach could enhance the process and lead to more comprehensive results. Even with a small number of respondents, this would allow for more targeted and specific discussions around the survey questions. A more active participation from respondents could provide valuable insights. Therefore, conducting a second round of discussions with the users to review their feedback would be beneficial for identifying additional features and opinions.

It is important to effectively implement the UCD methodology, which requires constant interaction between users and the technical experts developing the technology. This collaboration is essential for ensuring the success of the tools being developed. A lack of communication can lead to misunderstanding about the true purpose of the design, particularly because the stakeholders involved in developing data management and visualisation platforms often have different backgrounds, objectives, and perceptions of the technologies. In short, failure to adequately follow a UCD methodology results in the creation of non-functional tools for end-users, thus leading to their failure. Adopting a UCD methodology tailored to the agricultural sector's specific needs, along with continuous feedback from end-users, is a challenging but beneficial procedure. This type of methodology opens a communication channel between the stakeholders involved in the development and the users. In our case, the iterative feedback from farmers, researchers, and advisors has proven essential to developing a more realistic product adapted to the needs of the users.

In future work, in order to complement the entire process defined by the ISO 9241:210 standard, we will iterate integrating the end-user feedback in order to create a prototype that manages the distinct services considered in the DSE developed during the DIVINE project. To this end, the most relevant functionalities and features of data visualisations detected during this process will be configured and integrated in flexible prototypes. Indeed, these prototypes will be created and evaluated by the end-users, in order to create final data management and visualisation tools are best suited for a agricultural data ecosystem.

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Appendix A. Pilot Description

Table A1. Description of target sector and use cases associated with pilots involved in the DIVINE H2020 European project.

Id	Pilot	Target Sector	Use Case
R1	Data Space for sustainable food production	Farming, livestock	Livestock benchmarking platform for (a) optimizing milk production and pork production advisory service and (b) monitoring of carbon footprint on these farms.
R2	Crop yield prediction model	Crop production, digital agriculture, crop management	This pilot will look at what critical data sources can be accessed and are available both from private and public data sources and if these are combined with respect to the management of a crop production strategy what additional power of decision-making can the integrated data stream bring to the supply chain.
R3	Smart Farming data in the service of the new CAP monitoring	Cross-sectoral including arable and fruits, with cotton, olives, grapes, and peaches as crops.	Farm Management Information Systems (FMIS) utilised by farmers integrated with data spaces acting as a significant source of information and able to provide ground truth evidence in support of new CAP monitoring indicators.
R4	Potential effects of agricultural data sharing on traditional Olive and Almond Plantations	Organic olive and almond sectors	Agricultural data sharing.

Appendix B. Survey Template

Survey Template

1 How relevant are these aspects for you?

	1	2	3
1.1 Be able to visualize your own data:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
1.2 Be able to visualize others' data:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

2 Indicate the priority of the following visualisation tools or services:

- 2.1 Parcel identification:
- 2.2 Data description through tables and maps:
- 2.3 Benchmarking service:
- 2.4 Data downloading
- 2.5 Data uploading:
- 2.6 Connection and visualisation to private and public weather data:
- 2.7 Concrete formula application:
- 2.8 Decision support system:
- 2.9 See the status of Agricultural DSE requests:

3 Features of the table:

- 3.1 Colours:
- 3.2 Highlight relevant information:
- 3.3 Be able to display more than one plot on each table:

4 What would you highlight as a positive aspect of the way the tables are represented?

Write short answer:

5 What would you highlight as a negative aspect of the way the tables are represented? How would you improve it?

Write short answer:

6 Features of the chart:

- 6.1 Colours:
- 6.2 Highlight relevant information:
- 6.3 Be able to display more than one plot on each chart:

7 What would you highlight as a positive aspect of the way the charts are represented?

Write short answer:

8 What would you highlight as a negative aspect of the way the charts are represented? How would you improve it?

Write short answer:

9 Do you have any other comments or suggestions?

Write short answer:

Appendix C. Statistics*Appendix C.1. Multiple-Choice Questions*

Appendix C.1.1. Based on the Profiles

Table A2. Correlations between the different 'profiles' and the answers for Q2, Q3, and Q6 questions.

Question	Subquestion	Statistics		Result
		χ^2	<i>p</i> -Value	
Q2	1	1.200	0.548	Not Significant
	2	0.799	0.670	Not Significant
	3	1.200	0.878	Not Significant
	4	2.400	0.662	Not Significant
	5	1.714	0.788	Not Significant
	6	2.785	0.594	Not Significant
	7	3.885	0.421	Not Significant
	8	5.520	0.063	Not Significant
	9	1.200	0.878	Not Significant
Q3	1	1.714	0.424	Not Significant
	2	0.480	0.786	Not Significant
	3	0.799	0.670	Not Significant
Q6	1	0.480	0.786	Not Significant
	2	0.799	0.670	Not Significant
	3	0.799	0.670	Not Significant

Appendix C.1.2. Based on the Target Groups

Table A3. Correlations between the different ‘target groups’ and the answers for Q1, Q2, Q3, and Q6 questions.

Question	Subquestion	Statistics		Result
		χ^2	<i>p</i> -Value	
Q1	1	0.872	0.350	Not Significant
	2	0.120	0.729	Not Significant
Q2	1	0.075	0.784	Not Significant
	2	0.000	1.000	Not Significant
	3	1.200	0.548	Not Significant
	4	2.400	0.301	Not Significant
	5	1.714	0.424	Not Significant
	6	0.428	0.807	Not Significant
	7	1.028	0.597	Not Significant
	8	0.120	0.729	Not Significant
	9	1.200	0.548	Not Significant
Q3	1	0.274	0.600	Not Significant
	2	0.000	1.000	Not Significant
	3	0.000	1.000	Not Significant
Q6	1	0.000	1.000	Not Significant
	2	0.000	1.000	Not Significant
	3	0.000	1.000	Not Significant

References

- Bongiovanni, R.; Lowenberg-DeBoer, J. Precision agriculture and sustainability. *Precis. Agric.* **2004**, *5*, 359–387. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Cantini, C.; Nepi, P.E.; Avola, G.; Riggi, E. Direct and indirect ground estimation of leaf area index to support interpretation of NDVI data from satellite images in hedgerow olive orchards. *Smart Agric. Technol.* **2023**, *5*, 100267. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Alexopoulos, A.; Koutras, K.; Ali, S.B.; Puccio, S.; Carella, A.; Ottaviano, R.; Kalogeras, A. Complementary use of ground-based proximal sensing and airborne/spaceborne remote sensing techniques in precision agriculture: A systematic review. *Agronomy* **2023**, *13*, 1942. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Najdenko, E.; Lorenz, F.; Dittert, K.; Olfs, H.W. Rapid in-field soil analysis of plant-available nutrients and pH for precision agriculture—A review. *Precis. Agric.* **2024**, *25*, 1–30. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Phang, S.K.; Chiang, T.H.A.; Happonen, A.; Chang, M.M.L. From satellite to uav-based remote sensing: A review on precision agriculture. *IEEE Access* **2023**, *11*, 127057–127076. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Pande, C.B.; Moharir, K.N. Application of hyperspectral remote sensing role in precision farming and sustainable agriculture under climate change: A review. In *Climate Change Impacts on Natural Resources, Ecosystems and Agricultural Systems*; Springer: Cham, Switzerland, 2023; pp. 503–520.
- Santana, L. Data Integration for Precision Agriculture—Challenges and Opportunities for the Database community. *Esc. Reg. Banco Dados (ERBD) Bras.* **2022**, 123–126. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Choi, M.H.; Park, J.Y. Trends of Technologies and Standards for Digital Agriculture and Future Standardization Initiative. *Precis. Agric.* **2022**, *4*, 172.
- Bahlo, C.; Dahlhaus, P.; Thompson, H.; Trotter, M. The role of interoperable data standards in precision livestock farming in extensive livestock systems: A review. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* **2019**, *156*, 459–466. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Zhang, N.; Wang, M.; Wang, N. Precision agriculture—A worldwide overview. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* **2002**, *36*, 113–132. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Moysiadis, V.; Sarigiannidis, P.; Vitsas, V.; Khelifi, A. Smart farming in Europe. *Comput. Sci. Rev.* **2021**, *39*, 100345. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Kalmar, R.; Rauch, B.; Dörr, J.; Liggesmeyer, P. Agricultural Data Space. In *Designing Data Spaces*; Springer Nature: Cham, Switzerland, 2022.
- Otto, B.; ten Hompel, M.; Wrobel, S. *Designing Data Spaces: The Ecosystem Approach to Competitive Advantage*; Springer Nature: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 2022.
- Šestak, M.; Copot, D. Towards trusted data sharing and exchange in agro-food supply chains: Design principles for agricultural data spaces. *Sustainability* **2023**, *15*, 13746. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
- Tekinerdogan, B. Software Ecosystems for Precision Agriculture. In *Encyclopedia of Smart Agriculture Technologies*; Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 2023; pp. 1–10.

16. Mao, J.Y.; Vredenburg, K.; Smith, P.W.; Carey, T. User-centered design methods in practice: A survey of the state of the art. In Proceedings of the 2001 Conference of the Centre for Advanced Studies on Collaborative Research, Toronto, ON, Canada, 5–7 November 2001; p. 12.
17. Septiani, W.D.; Utami, S.; Putra, O.P.; Hikmah, N.; Handayani, P.; Narti, N. Designing of agricultural product e-marketplace by using UCD method. *J. Khatulistiwa Inform.* **2021**, *7*, 88–93. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
18. Xu, J.; Lu, Y.; Deng, B. OpenWeedGUI: An Open-Source Graphical Tool for Weed Imaging and YOLO-Based Weed Detection. *Electronics* **2024**, *13*, 1699. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
19. Andrienko, G.; Andrienko, N.; Drucker, S.M.; Fekete, J.D.; Fisher, D.; Idreos, S.; Kraska, T.; Li, G.; Ma, K.L.; Mackinlay, J.D.; et al. Big data visualization and analytics: Future research challenges and emerging applications. In *BigVis 2020: Big Data Visual Exploration and Analytics*; MIT: Cambridge, MA, USA, 2020.
20. Abras, C.; Maloney-Krichmar, D.; Preece, J. User-centered design. *Bainbridge W. Encycl. Hum.-Comput. Interact. Thousand Oaks Sage Publ.* **2004**, *37*, 445–456.
21. LIFT Consortium. LIFT: Low-Input Farming and Territories. 2024. Available online: <https://www.lift-h2020.eu/> (accessed on 30 July 2024).
22. DEMETER Consortium. DEMETER: Horizon 2020 Project (857202). 2024. Available online: <https://h2020-demeter.eu/> (accessed on 30 July 2024).
23. DIVINE Consortium. DIVINE: Demonstrating Value of agri Data Sharing for boosting Data Economy in Agriculture. 2024. Available online: <https://divine-project.eu/> (accessed on 30 July 2024).
24. Palma, R.; Roussaki, I.; Döhmen, T.; Atkinson, R.; Brahma, S.; Lange, C.; Routis, G.; Plociennik, M.; Mueller, S. Agricultural information model. In *Information and Communication Technologies for Agriculture—Theme III: Decision*; Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 2022; pp. 3–36.
25. Few, S.; Edge, P. Why Most Dashboards Fail. Perceptual Edge. 2007. Available online: <https://www.perceptualedge.com/articles/misc/WhyMostDashboardsFail.pdf> (accessed on 30 July 2024).
26. ISO 9241-210:2019; UNE-EN ISO 9241-210:2019 (Ratificada); Ergonomía de la Interacción Hombre-Sistema—Parte 210: Diseño Centrado en el Operador Humano Para los Sistemas Interactivos (Ratificada por la Asociación Española de Normalización en Noviembre de 2019). Vigente, ICS: 13.180 (Ergonomía), 35.180 (Terminales y otros equipos periféricos). ISO: Geneva, Switzerland, 2019.
27. Ilias, P.; Coca, P. Data Spaces for enabling AI solutions in AgriFood. The current situation, the opportunities and the forces. In Proceedings of the European Big Data Value Forum, Valencia, Spain, 26 October 2023.
28. Carrasco, J.Á.F.; Muñoz-Solanas, L.; Gil, L.S.; Paredes-García, D. CredSSI: Enhancing Security and Privacy with Self-Sovereign Identities Approach. In Proceedings of the 2024 IEEE International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications Workshops and other Affiliated Events (PerCom Workshops), Biarritz, France, 11–15 March 2024; pp. 745–750.
29. Liu, M.X.; Sarkar, A.; Negreanu, C.; Zorn, B.; Williams, J.; Toronto, N.; Gordon, A.D. “What it wants me to say”: Bridging the abstraction gap between end-user programmers and code-generating large language models. In Proceedings of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, Hamburg, Germany, 23–28 April 2023; pp. 1–31.
30. Hoffmann, V.; Probst, K.; Christinck, A. Farmers and researchers: How can collaborative advantages be created in participatory research and technology development? *Agric. Hum. Values* **2007**, *24*, 355–368. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
31. Carey, T. User differences in interface design. *Computer* **1982**, *15*, 14–20. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
32. Miller, R.B. The human task as reference for system interface design. In Proceedings of the ACM/SIGGRAPH Workshop on User-oriented Design of Interactive Graphics Systems, Pittsburgh, PA, USA, 14–15 October 1976; pp. 97–100.
33. Bolfe, É.L.; Jorge, L.A.d.C.; Sanches, I.D.; Luchiani Júnior, A.; da Costa, C.C.; Victoria, D.d.C.; Inamasu, R.Y.; Grego, C.R.; Ferreira, V.R.; Ramirez, A.R. Precision and digital agriculture: Adoption of technologies and perception of Brazilian farmers. *Agriculture* **2020**, *10*, 653. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
34. Allemang, D.; Teegarden, B. A global data ecosystem for agriculture and food. *F1000Research* **2017**, *6*, 1844.
35. Hackfort, S. Patterns of inequalities in digital agriculture: A systematic literature review. *Sustainability* **2021**, *13*, 12345. [\[CrossRef\]](#)
36. Pappas, L.; Whitman, L. Riding the technology wave: Effective dashboard data visualization. In *Proceedings of the Human Interface and the Management of Information. Interacting with Information: Symposium on Human Interface 2011, Held as Part of HCI International 2011, Orlando, FL, USA, 9–14 July 2011*; Proceedings, Part I; Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 2011; pp. 249–258.
37. Inkscape. Inkscape Project, 2020. Available online: <https://inkscape.org> (accessed on 8 October 2024).

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